

THE USE OF THE “NUR” METHOD IN TEACHING PHYSICS

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Annotation:This article discusses the new developments in the field of education today,the laws being adopted,the attention paid to teachers.It also provides information on a new innovative method to use in physics lessons.

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We have set ourselves the great goal of building the foundation of the third Renaissance in our country, for which we must create an environment and conditions that will nurture new Khorezmians, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Baburs.

In this regard,first of all,the development of education and upbringing,healthy lifestyles,the development of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea,said the President.

Indeed, the issue of education is crucial in achieving the lofty goals we set for ourselves today.

At the heart of the development of any field is a decent and quality education,staff with modern knowledge and skills.The task of education today is to teach students to work independently in a growing information learning environment,the effective use of modern information technology in various fields and the rational use of information flow.The future of the country,the success of all industries and projects depends on educated people.Therefore,in the last four years,a lot of work has been done to improve the quality of education, to raise the status of teachers.

Awards are being established to encourage many teachers,such as a teacher

,a teacher of the year, an outstanding public educator,who has set an example in such difficult times.The more we pay tribute to the head of our state ,who has created such conditions by introducing a system of additional payments for the work done by teachers,whose salaries have increased significantly.While creating such conditions for us, we also need to increase the interest of students in science by organizing quality and interesting lessons.

Today's young people are more interested in organizing lessons in a non-traditional way,using innovative technologies and using different methods.So now we need to organize lessons not only with blackboard and chalk,but also with more diverse methods,ie innovative technologies in education.

Innovative educational technology is the organization of teaching and learning activities,including improving the efficiency of the educational process and improving new or qualitatively existing methods and tools for creating the best conditions for educational.

This means that we educators need to organize each lesson with new methods,methods of education.If we expand the range of such methods with our own methods and apply them in our lessons,it will be a great light upon light.

I recommend that my method called “ Light” be used by teachers to make their lessons fun.The reason we call this method “Light” is that the beginning of this method begins quickly,but there is no end.As you move into the upper grades ,a variety of new physical terms will be added to this table.Teachers give students assignments Divide the student notebook into 4 columns.

Write column size in column 1,symbol in column2,unit in column 3,and tool in column 4. The name of the size of the 1st column is speed,path,time,presure,force.Assignment to column 2 v,s,t,P,F. 3-column unit m/s,m,s,Pa,N.

This method helps students to memorize physical quantities and units,instruments more quickly.Those who are interested in chemistry can quickly memorize the

elements and their sequence numbers using this method. This method can be used in all classes. When the light method is used in the consolidation of lessons and in repetition, generalization, and question-and-answer sessions, it will be easier for student to memorize the names of quantities, units, and tools in the topics covered.

SIZE	SIGN	UNIT	TOOL
Speed	v	m/s	Speedometer
The way	s	m	Meters
Time	t	s	Hour
Pressure	P	Pa	Barometer
Power	F	N	Dynamometer